

UTILIZATION OF STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL FOR READING AND WRITING IN ADDRESSING ASSESSMENT GAPS (PHASE I)

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Utilization of Strategic Intervention Material for Reading and Writing in Addressing Assessment Gaps (Phase I)

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Abstract

This study aimed to address and mitigate the gaps in assessment and performance among senior high school students taking the core subject Reading and Writing. This initiative aimed to enhance educational outcomes and promote a MATATAG future for every Filipino child by tackling significant issues in key learning competencies. Utilizing diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments, the project identified specific areas of struggle and implemented targeted interventions. The methodology included crafting strategic intervention materials and developing a remediation plan within instructional time. Results indicated substantial improvements across all targeted competencies, with the mean percentage scores (MPS) increasing significantly and failure rates decreasing in MELC 1, MELC 2, and MELC 3. The major findings highlight the effectiveness of tailored educational support and strategic interventions in improving student performance. Participant feedback revealed challenges in grammar, sentence construction, and vocabulary, emphasizing the need for foundational skill development. The implications of this study are far-reaching, demonstrating that with proper support and resources, significant academic improvements are achievable. Project SAGIP not only addressed immediate learning gaps but also provided a framework for future educational programs aimed at enhancing student performance and fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Keywords: *Project SAGIP, assessment gaps, educational performance, strategic intervention materials, remediation*

Introduction

Currently, proficiency in reading and writing is crucial for academic success and lifelong learning. Despite its importance, many students, particularly those in senior high school, continue to face significant challenges in mastering these competencies. Recent results from the Programme for International Student

Assessment (PISA) have highlighted significant deficiencies in the reading and writing skills of students in our education system. These results have drawn attention to the urgent need for effective interventions to improve student performance and ensure they meet global standards. In response, the Department of Education has advocated for the Matatag Curriculum, which emphasizes foundational literacy and numeracy skills, aiming to create a more robust and effective educational framework.

Initially, this study is part of Project SAGIP (Surpassing Assessment Gap for Improved Performance) which was initiated in response to identified gaps in reading and writing performance among learners, where results of assessment revealed persistent deficiencies in these fundamental skills. The primary tool employed in this initiative is the Strategic Intervention Material (SIM), designed to provide targeted support and remedial instruction to struggling learners.

In practice, the academic cycle often concludes with summative assessments, leaving the process incomplete without addressing the gaps identified. This approach overlooks the critical need for interventions based on assessment data to help students who lag behind. Thus, the cycle should not end at assessment but continue with targeted strategies to address identified weaknesses and support continuous improvement.

The study aims to address the lack of comprehensive evidence on the effectiveness of Strategic Intervention Materials in improving reading and writing competencies among learners who have consistently underperformed. While SIMs have been widely used, there is limited empirical data to support their impact on student outcomes in a systematic and measurable way.

Innovation, Intervention, or Strategy

The intervention strategy employed in this study is the utilization of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) specifically designed to address reading and writing competencies. This intervention is a critical component of Project SAGIP (Surpassing Assessment Gap for Improved Performance), aiming to provide specialized support to

learners who fail to meet the required standards in these core subjects. The process involves the use of SIMs following summative assessments. If learners do not achieve the desired competencies, they undergo a targeted intervention using these materials, which are tailored to address specific gaps. The materials are created for each competency and are structured to allow students to work independently while also providing necessary support through brief, targeted instruction.

The implementation of SIMs follows a structured procedure: First, summative assessments are conducted to identify learners who have not met the required competencies in reading and writing. Then, identified learners are provided with SIMs that correspond to their specific areas of need. Additionally, 15-minute special lectures are conducted to address specific needs, despite the materials

being self-based. Learners are then allowed to work through the SIMs independently, ensuring that the activities are aligned with the tasks and objectives. Continuous assessment is conducted through ongoing assessments embedded within the SIMs. Finally, feedback and additional support are provided as needed based on the learners' progress.

As mentioned, this study initially is a product of Project Sagip and this intervention aimed to offer a structured and targeted approach to remedial instruction, ensuring that learners receive the necessary support to meet competency standards. The extent of this intervention includes all students who fail to meet the standards in reading and writing, providing them with tailored materials and support. However, the intervention is limited by the availability of resources and the need for teacher involvement in conducting special lectures and providing ongoing support.

The intervention was implemented during the academic year 2023-2024 following the summative assessments. It was conducted in various schools participating in Project SAGIP, involving teachers, students, and school administrators. The primary resources used included the Strategic Intervention Materials, which consisted of the following parts as outlined in DepEd Memo No. 225, s. 2009: Title Card, which provides an overview of the material; Guide Card, which includes a detailed guide to the lesson, learning competency, and subtasks; Activity Card, which contains activities designed to concretize learning competencies and develop mastery; Assessment Card, which provides exercises to assess the level of mastery upon completion of activities; Enrichment Card, which includes additional activities to reinforce the lesson content; and Reference Card, which lists resources for further reading and learning.

Action Research Questions

Primarily, this study aims to address the assessment gaps of learners in Reading and Writing. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of learners after the summative task?
2. What intervention materials may be used to address the learners who failed to meet the standards?
3. What changes in performance mastery levels are observed in students after the implementation of SIMs?
4. What factors contribute to the success or failure of the intervention for these learners?

Methodology

Participants

The participants of this study consist of 216 learners from sections handled by the researcher. These learners underwent a summative assessment, with the intervention tailored based on their performance in each Most Essential Learning Competency (MELC). Specifically, the participants were categorized as follows: MELC 1 included 52 learners, MELC 2 comprised 92 learners, and MELC 3 had 37 learners. Most participants are from the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand. The selection of participants was performance-based, with no formal sampling techniques applied, thus it did not utilize purposive sampling. Instead, all learners who failed the summative assessment before the intervention were included in the study. This approach ensures that the intervention targets those who are struggling. The rationale behind this selection is to directly address the learning needs of students who performed poorly, allowing for a focused evaluation of how the intervention impacts their performance. Additionally, all 216 students took the post-intervention test to compare the Mean Percent Scores (MPS) and evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention.

Instrument

The data collection process began with administering summative tasks to the participants, with their scores recorded and interpreted to determine their performance levels. The Mean Percentage Score (MPS) for each learner was calculated based on these initial summative tasks. This data provided a clear measure of learners' understanding and performance before the intervention phase began.

Following the collection and analysis of pre-intervention data, the intervention phase commenced. During this phase, targeted support was provided to the learners based on their performance in the summative tasks. After the intervention, a post-intervention test was administered to assess any changes in the learners' performance. The results of this post-test were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention by comparing them with the pre-intervention scores.

This approach ensured that the data collection method was well-suited to the nature and purpose of the research, as it allowed for a direct comparison of learner performance before and after the intervention. The research instrument, consisting of summative tasks and subsequent tests, has undergone content validation from teacher practitioners who teach Reading and Writing.

Data Analysis

This study employs both quantitative and qualitative approach to evaluate the impact of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) in improving reading and writing competencies among learners. The analysis primarily focuses on quantitative methods, with qualitative insights serving to complement the findings.

Quantitative data were organized and analyzed using descriptive statistics. This included frequency counts to measure the number of learners who failed before the intervention and those who succeeded afterward. Performance comparisons were made by calculating

the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) before and after the intervention. Variance analysis was also performed to assess the extent of change in both the number of learners failing and the MPS.

Descriptive statistics were chosen for their simplicity and practicality in providing a clear overview of the intervention's impact. Frequency counts and variance calculations offer straightforward metrics that facilitate easy interpretation and comparison of performance data. This method allows for direct assessment of the effectiveness of the SIMs by highlighting changes in learner performance.

In addition to the quantitative analysis, qualitative data were collected through interviews with learners who did not meet the standards despite the intervention. Semi structured interviews were conducted to explore learners' experiences with the SIMs, focusing on their perceptions of the intervention's effectiveness, any difficulties they encountered, and their suggestions for improvement. The interview transcripts were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns. This qualitative aspect provides context to the quantitative findings, offering a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by learners and informing potential improvements to the intervention.

Results and Discussion

What is the level of performance of learners after the summative task?

Table 1. Performance Analysis of Learners by MELC After Summative Assessment

MELC	Total number of learners	Learners who failed the summative task	MPS	Learners who passed	Pass Rate (%)
1	215	52	61.49	163	75.81395
2	216	92	57.47	124	57.40741
3	215	37	66.03	178	82.7907

Following the summative assessment, the analysis of learner performance across the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) reveals significant insights into their understanding and application of key skills. MELC 3, which focuses on identifying claims explicitly or implicitly made in a written text, demonstrated the highest level of learner proficiency. With a pass rate of 82.79% and a mean percent score (MPS) of 66.03, it is evident that learners excelled in recognizing and interpreting claims within texts. This strong performance suggests that students have effectively developed the skills necessary for critical reading and comprehension in this area (Baker & Brown, 1984).

In contrast, MELC 2, which requires the evaluation of a written text based on its properties—such as organization, coherence, cohesion, language use, and mechanics—showed a lower level of learner achievement. The pass rate for this competency was 57.41%, with an MPS of 57.47, indicating that a significant portion of learners faced difficulties in analyzing text properties comprehensively. This lower performance may reflect challenges in understanding and applying complex evaluative criteria to written texts (Gordon & Browne, 2014).

MELC 1, which involves comparing patterns of written texts across disciplines, had an intermediate performance level with a pass rate of 75.81% and an MPS of 61.49. While this result is higher than MELC 2, it still shows room for improvement compared to MELC 3. The moderate success in this area suggests that learners are reasonably adept at analyzing text patterns but may need further support to enhance their comparative analysis skills (Fitzgerald, 1995).

The analysis of summative assessment results highlights the need for further intervention primarily in MELC 2, which focuses on evaluating written texts based on their properties. With a pass rate of only 57.41% and a mean percent score of 57.47, it is evident that a significant number of learners—specifically, the 92 who failed before the intervention—struggled with this competency. This substantial gap in performance suggests that these students require additional support to improve their ability to analyze text properties effectively. In addition, 52 learners who did not pass MELC 1, which involves comparing and contrasting text patterns, will also benefit from targeted intervention to enhance their comparative analysis skills. While MELC 3 showed relatively strong performance, with 37 learners needing further support, the focus should be on providing intensive assistance to those struggling with MELC 2 and MELC 1 to ensure they achieve proficiency in these essential skills.

What intervention materials may be used to address the learners who failed to meet the standards?

To address learners who have failed to meet educational standards, Project SAGIP employs a set of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) that are instrumental in guiding educators through effective intervention strategies. The Guide Card serves as the foundational framework for the project, outlining its goals, objectives, and implementation strategies. It ensures that educators have a clear understanding of the project's purpose and their roles, facilitating alignment with curriculum standards and effective monitoring of

student progress (Liem, 2018). The Activity Card provides detailed instructions for specific, targeted activities designed to address identified learning gaps. These activities are meticulously aligned with the curriculum and tailored to meet individual student needs, thereby offering a structured approach to intervention (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

The Assessment Card is vital for evaluating the effectiveness of the interventions, detailing methods and tools for assessing student progress before, during, and after the intervention period. This systematic approach ensures that assessments are aligned with learning objectives and provides data for refining interventions as necessary (Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

Complementing these is the Enhancement Card, which focuses on enriching the learning experience by suggesting innovative and engaging lesson ideas. This card encourages educators to go beyond addressing basic learning gaps, promoting a more stimulating and supportive educational environment (Tomlinson, 2001).

Finally, the Reference Card acts as a quick reference guide, providing essential information such as key contacts, project timelines, and relevant resources. It ensures that educators have immediate access to crucial details and support, thereby facilitating smooth project implementation and coordination (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005).

The structured approach provided by the Guide, Activity, Assessment, Enhancement, and Reference Cards plays a critical role in improving educational outcomes and bridging learning gaps, thereby contributing significantly to student success and achievement.

What changes in performance mastery levels are observed in students after the implementation of SIMs?

Table 2. *Impact of Interventions on Learner Performance Across MELCs*

MELC	Total number of learners	Learners who failed the summative task	Learners who passed after the intervention	Variance	MPS before intervention	MPS After Intervention	Variance
1	215	52	33	-19	61.49	79.01	17.52
2	216	92	68	-24	57.47	73.24	15.77
3	215	37	26	-11	66.03	84.65	18.62

The analysis of intervention effectiveness across different MELCs reveals substantial improvements in learner performance, reflecting the impact of targeted instructional strategies. For MELC 1, which requires learners to compare and contrast patterns of written texts across disciplines, the intervention yielded a significant reduction in failure rates and a marked increase in performance. Initially, 52 learners failed the summative task, but after the intervention, 33 of these learners succeeded, resulting in a net reduction of 19 failing students. The mean percent score (MPS) improved significantly from 61.49 to 79.01, a gain of 17.52 points.

This notable increase demonstrates that the intervention effectively enhanced learners' ability to analyze and compare text patterns, addressing initial gaps in their understanding and application of comparative analysis skills (Hattie, 2009). This improvement is particularly meaningful as it highlights the intervention's success in boosting students' proficiency in a critical academic skill.

MELC 2, which focuses on evaluating written texts based on their properties such as organization, coherence, and cohesion, also saw considerable progress. Here, 92 learners initially failed the summative assessment, but 68 of these students passed after receiving targeted interventions. This reduction of 24 failing students reflects a positive shift in performance. The MPS for MELC 2 increased from 57.47 to 73.24, an improvement of 15.77 points.

This change underscores the intervention's effectiveness in helping learners better understand and apply evaluative criteria to written texts. The success in this area indicates that the interventions addressed specific difficulties learners had with text evaluation, enhancing their ability to critically assess and engage with various text properties (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

For MELC 3, which involves identifying claims explicitly or implicitly made in a written text, the data shows a notable impact of the intervention. Originally, 37 learners failed, but after the intervention, 26 succeeded, resulting in a decrease of 11 failing students. The MPS increased from 66.03 to 84.65, an impressive gain of 18.62 points.

This significant improvement highlights the intervention's success in enhancing learners' skills in identifying and understanding claims within texts. The progress observed in this MELC reflects the effectiveness of the intervention in developing critical comprehension skills, which are crucial for academic success and analytical thinking (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005).

The data indicates that the interventions provided a positive impact across all MELCs, leading to reduced failure rates and substantial improvements in mean percent scores.

These results demonstrate the positive impact of targeted instructional strategies in addressing specific learning gaps, thereby improving overall learner performance and comprehension skills. The success of these interventions underscores the importance of strategic support in fostering academic achievement and ensuring that learners meet educational standards.

What factors contribute to the success or failure of the intervention for these learners?

Table 3. *Challenges and difficulty encountered of learners after the intervention*

Extracts	Themes	Reflective Analysis
<i>Para saakin, nahirapan ako sa tamang pag construct ng mga sentence at sa writing idadagdag, narin ang mga punctuation marks at unfamiliar words nasanay na akong laging may grammar checker kaya hindi ako familiar sa tamang pagsulat at paggamit ng mga sentences.</i>	Difficulty in Sentence Construction and Punctuation Reliance on External Resources	The feedback demonstrates a high level of self-awareness among the respondents regarding their areas of weakness in language skills. They openly acknowledge struggles with grammar, punctuation, vocabulary, and reading comprehension, indicating a willingness to confront and address these challenges.
<i>Based on my experience, I found it difficult to form a good statement and paragraph, and because I frequently use Google's Paraphraser, sometimes I get confused when making a paragraph on my own because the grammar or punctuation might be wrong. In other words, I have no trust in myself. I also struggle with English, particularly with grammar, and sometimes I forget the basic rules but I will try my best to learn and practice good writing.</i>	Reliance on External Resources Struggles with Grammar and Language Fluency Limited Vocabulary and Interpretation Skills:	A common theme across the feedback is the reliance on external resources, such as grammar checkers or online tools, for assistance with editing and proofreading. While these resources can be helpful, the feedback highlights a lack of confidence in self-editing abilities and the need to develop greater autonomy in revising written work.
<i>Madali lang naman ang capitalization and kung paano gamitin ang punctuation pero nahirapan ako medyo dun sa pag construct ng sentences especially nalilito ako sa Rule ng Grammar and also medyo nagkakaroon ako double thoughts kaya medyo natagalan ako sa pagsasagot. But I believe, maeenhance ko pa ang lesson na ito , especially in writing good and logical sentences.</i>	Struggles with Grammar and Language Fluency	Many respondents express difficulties with English grammar and language fluency, particularly in constructing coherent sentences and interpreting written material. This reflects a need for focused practice and reinforcement of foundational grammar skills to improve language proficiency.
<i>for me, nahirapan ako dun sa part ng MELC na may explicit and</i>	Limited Vocabulary and Interpretation Skills	Actively work on expanding vocabulary through daily

<p><i>implicit. Kasi here, halos magkatulad na yung dalawang bagay and medyo nag overthink ako sa mga sagot. Kase naman po ang confusing talaga nung dalawa. Also po dun sa pag eedit ng tamang pag construct ng grammar because naka asa na lang po ako internet kapag nag c-check ng grammar kaya nung pinagawa kami nun, madami po kong maling answers. But I'm still thankful na may bago akong natutunan sa subject na ito.</i></p>	<p>Struggles with Grammar and Language Fluency</p> <p>Reliance on External Resources:</p>	<p>reading of diverse materials such as books, articles, and online resources. Keep a vocabulary journal to record new words encountered and their meanings, and practice incorporating these words into writing exercises. Engage in vocabulary-building activities such as word games, flashcards, and quizzes to reinforce retention and usage.</p>
<p><i>Nahirapan po ako dahil po siguro nalimutan ko na ang mga basic grammar rules, and also hindi po ako masyadong na-expose sa mga unfamiliar words kaya nahahirapan po akong i-interpret yong ibang mga sentences. Nahirapan din po ako sa part na alamin kung alin ba ang bias at mali sa isang sentence. I think ang kailangan ko pong gawin ay mas palawakin pa ang vocabulary ko para naman po mas madali kong ma-interpret yong mga sentences at mas maging madali rin para sakin ang pag-coconstruct.</i></p>	<p>Struggles with Grammar and Language Fluency</p> <p>Limited Vocabulary and Interpretation Skills</p>	<p>Explore different strategies for analyzing and interpreting written material, such as identifying main ideas, supporting details, and author's perspective. Seek feedback from peers or instructors on interpretation exercises to gain insights and refine interpretation abilities.</p>

The reflective feedback from learners reveals several key areas where interventions could significantly improve their writing skills. The primary themes identified include difficulties in sentence construction and punctuation, reliance on external resources, struggles with grammar and language fluency, and limited vocabulary and interpretation skills.

Difficulty in Sentence Construction and Punctuation highlights a common issue where learners struggle to form grammatically correct and well-punctuated sentences. This difficulty often stems from a lack of understanding of grammar rules and the proper use of punctuation marks. Learners may become accustomed to using grammar checkers and similar tools, which can lead to an over-reliance on these resources instead of developing their own writing skills. According to Harris (2017), while external tools can provide valuable assistance, they should complement rather than replace foundational learning. This dependency may result in learners not fully internalizing grammar rules and punctuation, which impacts their ability to write independently and accurately.

The Reliance on External Resources is another significant theme. Many learners express that they rely heavily on tools like grammar checkers or paraphrasing services, which suggests a lack of confidence in their ability to self-edit and revise their work. This reliance may hinder their development of essential writing skills and contribute to a cycle of dependency. As Truscott (2007) notes, effective writing instruction should aim to build learners' internal editing capabilities rather than fostering a reliance on external aids. Encouraging learners to practice and refine their writing skills without constant external support can help them become more confident and competent writers.

Struggles with Grammar and Language Fluency reflect broader challenges in writing. Learners often find it difficult to construct coherent sentences and maintain fluency in their writing. This issue is linked to gaps in their understanding of basic grammar rules

and their ability to apply these rules consistently. Truscott (2007) suggests that targeted practice and instruction in grammar can improve fluency and overall writing quality. Focused grammar exercises and explicit teaching of grammatical structures can help learners build a stronger foundation and enhance their writing skills.

Limited Vocabulary and Interpretation Skills also emerge as critical areas for improvement. Learners report difficulties with understanding and using unfamiliar words, which affects their ability to interpret and construct sentences effectively. Nation (2013) emphasizes the importance of vocabulary expansion for improving reading comprehension and writing ability. Strategies such as extensive reading, maintaining a vocabulary journal, and engaging in vocabulary-building activities can help learners enhance their word knowledge and usage. Expanding vocabulary not only aids in constructing more varied and precise sentences but also improves overall interpretation and comprehension skills.

The feedback indicates that while learners face challenges with grammar, punctuation, vocabulary, and writing fluency, targeted interventions can address these issues effectively. By focusing on reducing reliance on external tools, reinforcing grammar rules, expanding vocabulary, and practicing self-editing, educators can help learners develop stronger writing skills and greater confidence in their abilities. Implementing these strategies in instructional practices will be crucial for supporting learners in overcoming their writing challenges and achieving academic success.

Action Plan

The researcher plans to disseminate and utilize the findings from their study on Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) through several strategic approaches to enhance educational policies, systems, and practices. The results will be presented at educational conferences and seminars and published in peer-reviewed journals to reach a broad audience of educators, policymakers, and academic peers. This will provide a formal platform to share evidence-based recommendations and demonstrate the effectiveness of the intervention strategies. Insights from the research will also be integrated into curriculum development, guiding the creation of more effective teaching materials and instructional approaches. To support educators, the researcher will organize workshops and training sessions focused on implementing and utilizing SIMs, thereby improving teaching practices and student learning experiences. Additionally, the findings will be used to advocate for policy changes that promote evidence-based practices and strategic interventions in education. Establishing feedback mechanisms will allow for continuous improvement of the SIMs based on input from educators and learners. Through these efforts, the researcher aims to contribute to meaningful improvements in educational practices, ultimately enhancing student outcomes and teaching methodologies.

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